

D7.4 API software for data ingestion and system integration – Month 18

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Short Description	
The report presents the work in laying ancillary shared systems for the tools. It also explains the work done in integrating the living lab in the overall infrastructure and how the work is going to be generalized for the pilots.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Models
BMS	Building Management Systems
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DMZ	Demilitarized Zone
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
PDH	Personalized Data Hub
ROI	Return on Investment
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SQL	Structured Query Language
TLS	Transport Layer Security

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Report summarises the work carried out so far and specifies the software and the ingestion/integration stack that will expose operational sensor data through a unified, dataspace-ready interface. To accomplish that objective, three components that divide the whole ingestion process, were developed in the following subtasks: turn data sources into endpoints for dataspace connection; transform endpoint data into a canonical format serving normalized tuples in the form {Sensor ID, date, value}; and running batch scripts for direct data ingestion and generation of aggregated data. A persistent Sensor Identity & Mapping Registry keeps auditable pairings between each assigned sensor ID and its original SCADA tag triplet (and units), ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and stable downstream contracts.

In the different sections, ingestion components, along with the architectural context inside WILSON framework and deployment of infrastructure are depicted, providing an overview of definition of functionalities, selection of technologies and result of the alpha version of each. Also a layer of basic services for WP7 such as graphDB, Apache Airflow for orchestration, a MQTT broker for message queue communications, Postgres, MongoDB and Redis databases are explained in the report.

At this point in the project, the CIRCE's Living Lab facilities have been used for testing and deployment, leaving demo site integration for the final version of the task. This integration includes developments such as a platform for endpoint representation, software for database-related endpoint creation or Apache Airflow instances for aggregated data creation. The technical solution for each component and the interaction between them in the laboratory provides an overview of the future development in the final sites.

As outlined in the conclusion, the activities carried out so far have been focused around getting the living lab ready for interaction with the dataspace while laying the foundation for the rest of the pilots by stablishing canonical representations and extensible components. Demonstrating a functional, replicable framework that delivers the key capabilities envisioned for this stage. In the next project phase, the focus will shift to extending the reference setup to pilot sites while rolling out scheduled data ingestion, as well as the integration in project dataspace.

2. INTRODUCTION

The WILSON project has a heterogeneous set of pilot sites representing the different types of built environments that can be found in real life. This means that each pilot site has a different set up in terms of data availability and interfaces with the real world. This report is concerned with setting system integration and data ingestion to bring a layer of compatibility with this heterogeneous set ups.

Three main points for data ingestion and integration have been detected. The first point is the need to adapt to the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) architecture which requires data endpoints for integration. As such components are needed to turn data sources into http endpoints that can be connected to the dataspace. The second point is the heterogeneous nature of the sensor data. Sensor data streams are not planned to be part of the semantic repositories as the sheer volume of potential data would make it impractical considering the potential ROI. However, leaving the data as is would also require tailoring each tool to each pilot site. As a middle ground, a middleware that generates normalized data points providing a single format for sensor streams is proposed. This normalization middleware also provides a pairing registry which could be tied to semantic data, for example to indicate the sensor that produces the data stream as well as the other metadata such as the location of said sensor. Finally, an orchestration layer was also added leading to produce secondary aggregated data both to produce useful cached data and to perform task such as periodical updates in the links between data streams and semantic data.

In WILSON Living Lab, the above-mentioned points have been managed in different ways. The first issue has been addressed with a reusable component that creates read only endpoints from relational databases ensuring access without compromising the original system. For the second issue, a service that guides the user in mapping the generated endpoints into normalized data streams has been developed. As for the third issue, a set of ancillary services for data storage, communications and orchestration have been deployed. The work has been designed bearing in mind replication potential, with most of the infrastructure containerized and by creating deployment scripts that can replicate the base layout in new machines.

The Living Lab is located at CIRCE's headquarters in Zaragoza, Spain, and consists of several offices and technical facilities within the same business area. During recent renovations, various innovative solutions were implemented, all of which are managed entirely by CIRCE. This autonomy guarantees a flexible environment managed by qualified personnel, allowing for the testing of various solutions in the context of sustainability and energy efficiency. The Living Lab has a SCADA system allowing access to various energy readings both of consumption as well as photovoltaic production and battery usage. Further description of WILSON Living Lab can be found in D9.2 [1].

2.1. Structure of the Report

The *Report* is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** provides the executive summary.

- **Section 2** introduces the objectives and context of this work within the WILSON framework.
- **Section 3** describes the compatibility layer for the living lab.
- **Section 4** describes the normalization layer and its application to the living lab.
- **Section 5** describes the scheduling and data ingestion methods.
- **Section 6** describes the server set up and its replicability
- **Sections 7 and 8** provide challenges, future work plan and conclusions, respectively.
- **Section 9** lists reference used in this report.
- **Annexes** contain user manuals for developed tools.

2.2. Relation with Other Tasks and Deliverables

- **WP5–6 Semantic and federated digital twins at local and district levels:** Transformations in our work align to ontologies and semantic models from WP5/WP6, ensuring PDH-ready data and consistent schemas across connectors and APIs.
- **WP7–8 Data interoperability for data mesh enabled digital twins:** Our work provides the ingestion methods and the stable API façade that feed PDHs with harmonised streams (e.g., time-series via {date, value, sensor ID}) which is developed in the T7.1. Furthermore, T7.2 develops access control with which T7.4 will have to interact in order to make the compatibility layers as transparent as possible.
- **WP9–10 Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses & WP11–12 Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for non-energy uses:** the normalised API developed in our work supports the rest of the tools by providing reliable and normalized historical/real-time access.

3. HTTP DATA ACCESS LAYER FOR ECLIPSE DATASPACE COMPATIBILITY

In several pilot sites, relevant operational data is stored within relational databases that are part of existing local systems. Integrating these data sources into the dataspace architecture requires a mechanism to expose them through a standardized interface without modifying their configuration or compromising their integrity.

The read-only HTTP data access layer has been developed to address this need. It provides a simple and secure way to query on-premises relational databases through authenticated REST endpoints while ensuring complete immutability of the data. The component acts as a compatibility bridge between the local database and the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC), enabling the registration of database tables as dataspace assets and allowing controlled access through existing EDC policies.

The design follows a clear principle: the data API must not alter the content, schema, or configuration of the database. Instead, it exposes read-only endpoints that allow the retrieval of information required by the dataspace participants. The component can be deployed on site, as a lightweight containerized service, and integrated with the EDC for secure access control at the data plane level.

3.1. Architectural Context and Integration in the WILSON Framework

Within the WILSON framework, this component functions as an intermediary between the existing local infrastructure and the dataspace environment. Many pilot systems already operate mature relational databases that manage building and energy data. Replacing these databases or duplicating their content into external systems would be impractical and risk data consistency.

The proposed read-only API provides a non-intrusive integration path. By offering HTTP access to relational data, it enables these systems to participate in the dataspace while preserving their autonomy. The architecture follows a microservice approach that includes a FastAPI backend, authentication middleware, and integration points for the EDC. The service can be deployed as part of the same Docker environment as the local EDC instance, simplifying orchestration and secure communication between components.

The API connects to the PostgreSQL instance using a read-only configuration, exposes standardized endpoints, and registers assets with the EDC so that other participants in the dataspace can discover and access them through governed contracts. This approach maintains alignment with the WILSON principle of data sovereignty, allowing data to remain under the control of its owner while still being accessible in a federated context.

3.2. Functional Overview

The component offers a structured set of functionalities designed to facilitate controlled access to relational data. It provides:

- RESTful interface for data retrieval
- Endpoints for listing tables, inspecting schemas, and querying records
- Advanced filtering capabilities for column-based conditions
- Configurable authentication mechanisms, including Basic Auth, OAuth2, and JWT (only basic auth implemented in the first iteration)
- Integration with the EDC for token validation and policy enforcement (to be done)

The main purpose of these functions is to create a transparent access layer that can be easily connected to the dataspace without requiring reconfiguration of the underlying databases. The data remains stored within the organization's environment, and the service only retrieves records in response to authenticated read requests.

The system has been tested to ensure it operates reliably across various database schemas, automatically discovering available tables and their metadata. This makes it adaptable to different pilot environments without the need for predefined database structures.

3.3. Security Design and Read-Only Enforcement

The central design requirement of this component is to guarantee that no operation can modify the underlying database. To achieve this, multiple layers of protection have been implemented:

1. **Database connection level:** The connection parameters enforce read-only transactions at all times through the settings `default_transaction_read_only=on` and `transaction_read_only=on`.
2. **Session level:** Each active session explicitly sets transaction characteristics to read-only and disables automatic commits and flushes.
3. **Application level:** The data service includes only SELECT and COUNT statements. All write operations such as INSERT, UPDATE, DELETE, or DDL are excluded from the codebase.
4. **API level:** The exposed routes are limited to GET requests. No endpoints supporting data modification exist.

In addition to these static protections, a verification routine runs automatically before the service starts. It performs test queries to confirm that write operations are blocked. If any of these checks fail, the service will refuse to start. The same mechanism logs the successful verification to provide evidence of compliance.

The overall security model ensures that even if the API were misused, the configuration of the PostgreSQL database would prevent any modification attempts. This multi-layer approach provides assurance that the data remains intact, even when accessed from external systems through the dataspace.

3.4. Database Analysis and Exposure Strategy

Before any database is exposed through the HTTP interface, a discovery process analyses its schema and identifies the elements that can be safely published. The process includes:

- Listing all tables available within the connected schema
- Retrieving column metadata, including types, constraints, and primary keys
- Identifying foreign key relationships to preserve referential context
- Detecting columns that may contain sensitive or restricted data

The API automatically generates schema descriptions that can be inspected through dedicated endpoints. This feature assists administrators in verifying which data elements are exposed and how they are represented. For performance and clarity, only selected tables and columns should be registered as dataspace assets. This selection process can be configured through environment parameters or by maintaining inclusion lists per table. The results of the discovery procedure also feed into the EDC asset registration workflow. Each published table or query endpoint can be mapped to a dataspace asset, enabling contract-based access and auditability while leaving the original database structure untouched.

3.5. Filtering and Query Mechanism

The filtering mechanism allows flexible querying of database tables without exposing arbitrary SQL statements. Each query is expressed as a combination of column names, operators, and values, using a controlled syntax verified by the service before execution.

Supported operators include equality, inequality, comparison ($>$, $<$, $>=$, $<=$), and pattern matching (LIKE, ILIKE). Filters can be combined to narrow down datasets according to user-defined conditions. The service automatically detects column data types and converts filter values accordingly, supporting integer, decimal, boolean, date, and text fields.

All filter parameters are validated to prevent SQL injection or other unsafe queries. The system checks that column names exist, that only whitelisted operators are used, and that the query remains within the permitted read-only scope. The maximum result size is limited to a configurable threshold to prevent heavy loads on production databases. This filtering mechanism provides sufficient flexibility to enable targeted data retrieval for EDC-linked assets, while maintaining strict safety boundaries. It represents a key feature for integrating heterogeneous pilot databases, allowing them to be queried in a consistent and secure manner.

3.6. Integration with Eclipse Dataspace Connector

The read-only HTTP API is designed to operate alongside the Eclipse Dataspace Connector by exposing database resources as HTTP endpoints that can later be mapped to dataspace assets. Defining these endpoints is a necessary step for EDC integration because assets and policies in the connector reference concrete, callable resources in the data plane.

At this checkpoint, the work focuses on preparing those endpoints and ensuring they are stable, authenticated, and strictly read-only. Actual connector integration—asset registration in the catalogue, contract negotiation flows, and policy-bound credential validation at runtime is not executed in this stage. These activities are planned for a later iteration, once pilot feedback on the exposed resources and query patterns is incorporated.

The current outcome is therefore an on-site API that can be adopted by the connector when integration proceeds. Each selected table or filtered view can be associated with a future asset description, and the API's authentication and pagination mechanisms are aligned with that target. This approach limits changes to existing systems, allows early validation of the access patterns required by the pilots, and leaves the connector-specific configuration and testing to the next milestone.

4. CANONICAL TUPLE NORMALIZATION SERVICE

The objective of the canonical data representation layer is to establish a stable and uniform data model capable of integrating heterogeneous sensor information from multiple operational endpoints. This layer ensures that all measurements, regardless of their origin or structure, are exposed through a common tuple form {sensorId, date, value}. The representation simplifies data access for downstream services and provides a consistent contract across pilots that supports downstream analysis and lightweight interchange.

At this checkpoint, the service consumes only the read-only HTTP endpoints implemented in the previous section and does not alter source systems. The approach keeps access authenticated and aligned with the existing read-only model and pagination conventions of the upstream API, which is already documented and consumable via standard HTTP clients.

4.1. Architectural context in the WILSON framework

The normalization service sits between on-premises read-only endpoints and consumers such as analytics pipelines or dashboards. It externalizes transformation and mapping so that operational databases remain unchanged. This is consistent with the layered system design described in the deliverable, where backend services expose capabilities without forcing schema changes on pilot infrastructures, and client components consume those capabilities via HTTP interfaces. This work is performed on the fly when the tools request data in order to avoid persistent data ingestion which might create stale data.

The service performs four main functions:

1. Enumerates available sources using the upstream table and schema endpoints.
2. Defines per-source mappings that bind columns to the canonical fields.
3. Applies normalization rules during fetch.
4. Serves normalized tuples through a simple HTTP interface with pagination. These functions build on the upstream API primitives for listing tables, inspecting schemas, retrieving data, and paginating responses.

4.2. Canonical data model and semantics

The canonical model represents all measurements using a minimal and predictable structure. Each record is composed of three primary fields:

- **sensorId:** a globally unique identifier assigned by the system to represent a physical or logical sensor, independent of its original source identity.
- **Timestamp:** the date and time of the observation, normalised to UTC and stored in ISO-8601 format.
- **data/value:** the measured quantity or, for multi-variable sensors, a structured JSON object containing key-value pairs.

The pair (sensorId, timestamp) is unique and acts as a natural key across all stored records. This convention enables idempotent upserts and deterministic re-processing providing traceability when data is re-computed or backfilled.

By enforcing this representation, all pilot sources can be queried and aggregated through a single schema, ensuring consistency across the WILSON data ecosystem while paving the way to link sensor data streams with semantic data that explains the meaning of those data streams.

4.3. Sensor Identity and Mapping Registry

The Sensor Identity and Mapping Registry maintains the correspondence between each canonical sensor identifier and its originating system, table, and column identifiers. Each entry contains the canonical sensor UUID, the associated endpoint, the source table and column, and optional descriptive metadata such as the sensor name, type, or measurement unit.

Mappings are versioned with effective-from and effective-to dates to account for sensor replacements or schema changes. This ensures reproducibility when reprocessing historical data and supports clear provenance for data governance. This registry underpins both the transformation process and the canonical API.

4.4. Transformation and Normalisation Process

Transformation from raw endpoint data into canonical form follows a three-step workflow:

1. **Extraction:** the system queries the configured endpoint for data within a defined table, using filters and pagination to retrieve manageable batches.
2. **Mapping:** users specify which source columns correspond to the canonical fields: one column for the sensor identifier, one for the timestamp, and one or more for the measurement values.
3. **Normalization:** the extracted data is converted to the canonical tuple structure. Data types are coerced, timestamps normalized to UTC, and measurement units harmonized when necessary.

The mapping between endpoints and the canonical representation is not hardcoded within the application. Instead, it is established interactively through user-defined configurations that determine how source columns correspond to the canonical tuple {sensorId, date, value}. This approach allows the system to adapt to heterogeneous data sources and schema variations without requiring code changes or redeployment.

When a user connects to an endpoint, the system retrieves the list of available tables and their respective schemas via the /tables and /schema API endpoints. Of course, this process relies on the endpoint structure of the tool developed in section 3. However, the structure is designed to accommodate more heterogeneous endpoints in the second iteration.

At this stage the web interface then displays the table structure, enabling the user to select:

- the column that represents the sensor identifier,
- the column containing the timestamp or measurement date, and
- one or more columns representing measurement values.

Once a configuration is saved, it is stored in the `transform_configurations` table of the internal database. Each configuration includes the endpoint reference, the source table name, the selected column mappings, and any applied filters or transformations. During data ingestion, this configuration is read and applied dynamically by the transformation engine, which interprets the user-defined mappings to construct the canonical tuples.

This mechanism ensures that the application remains decoupled from any specific schema or table naming convention. New data sources can be introduced by simply defining a corresponding mapping configuration through the same interface, without requiring additional backend development.

The mapping framework has been designed with extensibility in mind. Although it currently operates over PostgreSQL endpoints, the abstraction layer, that handles schema inspection and data retrieval, can be extended to other types of connectors. For each new connector type, the system will expose a unified metadata structure describing available fields, which the user can map to the canonical model in the same manner as database tables.

By delegating schema interpretation to configuration rather than code, the system achieves flexibility, transparency, and long-term maintainability. It enables non-developer users to adapt the service to new or changing data sources while ensuring that all resulting outputs continue to conform to the same canonical schema and data governance rules

4.5. Consistent rollout

Deployments follow the same directory layout and scripted steps, so new sites start from a known structure and reach a predictable end state. A small set of environment variables (ports, credentials, upstream endpoints) is the main source of site-specific change, which keeps image versions and compose files identical across locations. A minimal set of scripts supports the lifecycle: `replicate-structure.sh` creates the `folder/config` scaffold, `deploy-all.sh` brings services up in the right order, and `stop-all.sh` shuts them down safely while preserving data volumes unless removal is intended.

4.6. Canonical Query Interface

The canonical API provides access to normalized data through REST endpoints exposed by the FastAPI service. Clients can query measurements by sensor identifiers and time ranges, request pagination, and obtain results in JSON format. Optional query parameters allow filtering by date intervals or retrieving aggregated statistics at fixed resolutions.

Endpoints follow a versioned structure to ensure compatibility over time. The API is secured with the same authentication mechanisms as other WILSON services and complies with general REST conventions. It returns deterministic responses that can be directly consumed by PDHs and analytic tools. This interface constitutes the primary means by which harmonized sensor data can be accessed programmatically within the WILSON ecosystem. The canonical query interface also provides a way to generate more fine-grained endpoint from coarse ones, offering a way for us to manage more detailed access permissions for pilot data.

5. ORCHESTRATION AND SCHEDULING FRAMEWORK

This section describes the orchestration logic that coordinates data acquisition and aggregation workflows within the WILSON ingestion architecture. Apache Airflow has been adopted as the scheduling and workflow management system due to its flexibility, transparency, and compatibility with the project’s microservice-based architecture. Airflow ensures consistent execution across heterogeneous data sources, providing transparency, traceability, and recovery in case of failures.

The orchestration layer is designed to be able to integrate connectors described in Deliverable D7.3, triggering data acquisition from both legacy and third-party systems as well as with the canonical transformation and storage services developed in this task. The use of Airflow enables the configuration and monitoring of workflows that can be replicated and adapted for each pilot environment, supporting scalable and auditable data processing within the WILSON ecosystem.

At this point, the orchestration is ready but has not been fully integrated with the rest of the components. Overall integration of this layer will be done in the framework of WP8.

5.1. Airflow Setup and Configuration

Apache Airflow has been deployed as part of the common WILSON data infrastructure, sharing the same environment as the ingestion and canonical data services. The installation follows a containerized setup based on Docker Compose, which includes the Airflow scheduler, web server, worker nodes, and a metadata database. The configuration integrates with other project services such as Postgres, Redis, and FastAPI-based ingestion endpoints.

Each workflow in Airflow is defined as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), representing a sequence of dependent tasks that can be executed automatically according to a defined schedule or trigger. DAG definitions are written in Python and version-controlled within the project repository to ensure consistency across environments. Environment variables are used to parameterize file paths, connection strings, and pilot-specific configurations, enabling easy replication across sites.

The setup will incorporate access control and logging consistent with WILSON’s shared authentication policies. Access to the Airflow user interface is restricted to authorized users, and execution logs are persisted in the system database for traceability.

5.2. Integration with Data Acquisition Pipelines

The Airflow orchestration layer coordinates the execution of data ingestion pipelines that connect to heterogeneous systems via the connectors developed under Task 7.3. These connectors serve as the interface between local data sources such as Building Management Systems (BMS), databases, or third-party platforms and the Personalized Data Hub (PDH).

Within this setup, Airflow automates the following activities:

- Triggering data extraction from legacy or external systems using the PDH connectors.
- Launching transformation processes that convert raw data into the canonical representation (`{sensorId, date, value}`).
- Loading harmonized datasets into local databases or caching layers for subsequent access.

Examples include periodic batch loading of CSV and SQL datasets, IFC or Revit model conversions for semantic integration, and daily retrieval of weather data through public APIs. By scheduling and monitoring these operations, Airflow ensures that all upstream and downstream data flows remain synchronized and aligned with the temporal and semantic requirements of the WILSON framework.

The design follows a modular approach: each DAG corresponds to a specific ingestion scenario and can be enabled or adjusted independently. This modularity supports incremental expansion as additional pilot sites and connector types are introduced.

Each DAG specifies the timing, dependencies, and retry logic for its tasks, allowing flexible management of heterogeneous data sources and differing update frequencies.

Typical scheduling patterns include:

- **Daily or hourly ingestion tasks** for data sources that provide regular sensor updates or refreshed logs.
- **Weekly or monthly routines** for heavier transformations, such as BIM file conversions or IFC-to-LBD mappings.
- **Event-triggered workflows** for connectors that respond to external signals, such as updates from weather APIs or newly uploaded data files.

Monitoring and reliability are handled through Airflow's native features. Task statuses are visible through the web dashboard, allowing operators to track progress, identify delays, or review historical runs. When a task fails, Airflow automatically retrieves according to defined policies and logs diagnostic information for subsequent review.

5.3. Operational Integration and Future Extensions

The orchestration framework operates within the same deployment environment as other WILSON services, ensuring coherence between orchestration, data storage, and access control components. The setup leverages the containerized infrastructure described in Section 6, allowing the Airflow instance to be deployed on dedicated servers or replicated across pilot environments with minimal configuration changes.

When invoking data APIs or connectors, Airflow will use authenticated requests aligned with the access control mechanisms defined in Task 7.2. This ensures that automated data acquisition processes comply with the same security and policy requirements as manual access.

Future iterations will focus on integrating all the services into the orchestration layer. As the pilots expand, the orchestration layer will also serve as a foundation for coordinating distributed data acquisition across multiple sites, ensuring scalability and consistency across the WILSON ecosystem.

6. INFRASTRUCTURE DEPLOYMENT

The deployment provides a consistent, repeatable environment for the living lab that can be reused at pilot sites. It offers stable, governed access to operational data through clearly defined interfaces, while leaving source systems unchanged. The living-lab setup is the reference; pilots are expected to adjust only local details such as credentials, network ranges, and site policies.

6.1. Stable, governed data access

Services are composed to expose read-only or tightly scoped endpoints that present canonical views where needed. Interfaces are clearly bounded, limiting what each component consumes, produces, and is responsible for, so changes inside the stack do not propagate. The stack includes a workflow scheduler, an API/gateway, a messaging service, and persistence layers (graph, document, and relational databases), plus domain services for standardization and “endpointer” APIs. Each component has a documented role and, where necessary, a fixed host port, which simplifies firewalling, reverse-proxy routing, and monitoring.

6.2. Operational reliability

After deployment, a short, repeatable verification sequence confirms that containers are running, required networks exist, volumes are mounted, and key endpoints respond as expected. Operators rely on a concise set of commands for logs and status checks. Common recovery paths are documented to address the issues most frequently encountered—freeing a busy port, recreating the private network, correcting file/volume permissions, or fixing environment values and redeploying—before escalating with collected logs and configuration diffs.

6.3. Security by default

Security controls are applied at deployment time and can be aligned with local policy. Credentials are injected via environment configuration; services run with limited permissions where supported; only the necessary host ports are opened; encryption is enabled where components or a gateway support it; and development/test and production configurations are kept separate. Internal service-to-service communication happens on a private network created by the deployment; this keeps those conversations inside the system, not directly reachable from outside machines, and allows the setup to expose only a small number of public entry points (typically the gateway or designated APIs).

6.4. Containerization

All components run as Docker containers orchestrated with Docker Compose. Services join a shared network dedicated to internal communication. This keeps service-to-service traffic on a private path that external clients cannot directly access and allows the deployment to expose only a small number of public entry points (typically a gateway or designated APIs). Compose files and per-service configuration live in versioned directories to provide an auditable, declarative runtime definition.

The stack includes core runtime elements (e.g., workflow/orchestration, gateway, message broker, graph/document/relational datastores) and domain services (e.g., standardization, read-only endpointers). Each service has a documented role, internal hostname on the shared network, and a fixed port mapping when exposure on the host is required. This allows firewalling, reverse-proxy routing, and monitoring to be configured consistently.

6.4.1. Deployment automation

Developed shell scripts support a repeatable lifecycle:

- **replicate-structure.sh** clones the directory and config layout for a new site.
- **deploy-all.sh** creates the external network (if absent), brings up services in dependency order, and exits on failure.
- **stop-all.sh** performs a controlled shutdown, preserving volumes and network state unless explicitly removed. These scripts minimize drift between environments and reduce manual steps during rollout.

6.4.2. Environment management

New sites start from the reference living-lab layout, with the same folder and service structure as well as the same internal network and containers. Replication consists of cloning the structure, populating site-specific .env values, and running the deployment script sequence. Because service images and Compose definitions are shared, updates can be rolled out uniformly, while local differences (credentials, network ranges, firewall rules) are confined to environment files and gateway configuration. This approach enables predictable, low-variance deployments across pilots.

7. CHALLENGES, MITIGATIONS, AND NEXT STEPS

This section outlines the key issues observed in the living-lab rollout, how they were handled, and how they will be followed up in task T8.2.

7.1. Heterogeneous data sources and mappings

Challenge: Each pilot site uses different database structures, naming conventions, and units, complicating direct ingestion and normalization. Without harmonization, it is difficult to perform uniform queries or analyses.

Mitigation: A configurable mapping layer was introduced to translate site-specific structures into a minimal, shared schema (sensorId, timestamp, value, plus optional metadata). Each site maintains its own mapping configuration, versioned and documented separately from the code. This allows updates without redeployment and preserves the history of transformations.

Next steps: Link the sensor data streams with the semantic data repositories in order to provide metadata for the streams using airflow to run batch analysis of sensors and semantic data. Extend the mapping framework to improve replicability. Use scheduled data processing to generate enriched data for the tools.

7.2. Read-only access and data sovereignty

Challenge: Ensuring that no component writes to or alters the original source databases is essential to maintaining data sovereignty and operator trust.

Mitigation: Multiple safeguards enforce read-only behaviour: restricted database roles, read-only connections at the service level, and startup checks that fail if write operations are possible. The architecture exposes only derived or standardized data through the API layer, leaving original datasets untouched.

Next steps: Coordinate with T8.2 to audit data access and improve credential management. Improve the data access component to allow more restrictive access without compromising functionality.

7.3. Controlled exposure, performance, and reliability

Challenge: When exposing endpoints publicly, there is a risk of overexposure or excessive query load that could affect operational systems.

Mitigation: Endpoints to the living lab database are only exposed through the internal network.

Next steps: Conduct further performance validation and define limits to the reading APIs.

7.4. EDC alignment and authentication constraints

Challenge: The EDC Connector requires each asset to expose a callable HTTP endpoint but currently supports only limited authentication options. This restricts fine-grained access control and policy enforcement.

Mitigation: The present implementation provides stable, documented, TLS-protected endpoints with basic authentication. Exposure is deliberately narrow and limited to trusted consumers. The mapping application allows the creation of more fine-grained data access endpoints.

Next steps: Implement other EDC supported authentication methods such as OAuth and refine credential controls together with T8.2.

7.5. Operational consistency and change management

Challenge: Differences in local environments—such as file paths, port allocations, and firewall rules can introduce configuration drift and complicates troubleshooting. Similarly, schema or endpoint changes across releases can affect stability.

Mitigation: The use of a shared folder structure, scripted deployment lifecycle, and env-based configuration isolates these differences. All local modifications are confined to environment variables and configuration files rather than code. Versioning of mappings and endpoint definitions provides traceability and rollback options.

Next steps: Start pilot rollout where possible. Introduce post-deployment validation steps, including checks for network existence, container health, and endpoint reachability.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the work to achieve a replicable framework for data ingestion, normalization, and integration across heterogeneous systems. The work focused on designing a containerized, environment-driven setup that can be deployed consistently across different sites while preserving data sovereignty. The first full deployment was completed in the living lab, serving as a reference configuration and proof of concept for future pilot installations.

The work has produced a functioning and demonstrable integration framework that can be replicated and extended:

- **Operational infrastructure.** A containerized stack deployed in the living lab, including workflow scheduling, standardized API services, message brokering, and persistence components. The stack operates as an integrated environment, allowing the orchestration of ingestion and standardization workflows.
- **Data ingestion and normalization.** Configurable pipelines convert heterogeneous source structures into canonical forms without changing the underlying databases. Mappings are externally defined and traceable.
- **Governed and read-only access.** Data is exposed through stable, read-only endpoints that meet dataspace requirements for callable HTTP interfaces, while keeping local ownership and avoiding duplication.
- **Replicable deployment process.** A set of scripts (replicate, deploy, stop) and environment templates ensure predictable rollouts with minimal manual intervention. Each site can adapt configuration values such as ports, credentials, and endpoint definitions while maintaining identical container images.
- **Security and operational baselines.** Standardized configuration for credentials, limited port exposure, and health checks enable secure and consistent operation across environments.
- **Alignment with EDC principles.** Services are designed around clear interface boundaries and callable endpoints, forming a concrete foundation for future integration with EDC-managed assets and policies.

The living-lab deployment demonstrates a functional, replicable framework that delivers the key capabilities envisioned for this stage: consistent data ingestion, standardized read-only interfaces, and controlled deployment reproducibility. Challenges related to authentication, mapping evolution, and monitoring are recognized, and mitigation paths are in progress.

In the next project phase, the focus will shift to extending the reference setup to pilot sites. Each site will configure its local environment and credentials using the same scripts and definitions, ensuring alignment and minimizing drift. Upcoming tasks include expanding the mapping framework and rolling out scheduled data ingestion to create useful secondary data as well as coordinating with T8.2 for EDC integration.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, WILSON Partners *D9.2 Building energy use optimisation service – Month 18*. WILSON. Bruxelles : European Commision, 2025. HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-02 – Project 101147267.

10. ANNEX A. DATA STANDARIZER USER MANUAL.

This user manual gives a brief description of how the canonical endpoint generator service a.k.a. 'data standarizer' works.

10.1. Landing page

The landing page is the first point of entry to the platform. It presents the WILSON logo and project colours, ensuring consistency with the brand identity. A clear call-to-action button, "Enter Platform", directs users to the login screen.

Figure 1 Landing page in Data standarizer

10.2. Login

The login screen enables users to authenticate with the system. This is handled by a basic username and password flow using JWT tokens. Users are asked to enter their credentials and are granted access to the platform. Future iterations will integrate OAuth2/OIDC and/or Eclipse Dataspace ID.

Figure 2 Login in Data standardizer

10.3. Register

The Registration Page enables new users to create accounts and gain access to the WILSON Data Standardizer platform by providing essential user information and establishing their credentials. This page collects necessary details including a unique username, valid email address, and secure password, with built-in validation to ensure data integrity and security compliance. The registration process includes real-time validation feedback to help users create accounts that meet system requirements, such as unique username verification and password strength validation. Once the registration form is completed and submitted successfully, new users can immediately begin using the platform to configure data sources, set up column mappings, and access the canonical data API. The page provides clear instructions and helpful error messages to guide users through the account creation process smoothly.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `192.168.60.2:3000/register`. The page title is "Create Account" and the subtitle is "Join the WILSON Data Platform". The form contains the following elements:

- Username input field
- Email input field
- Organization input field
- Service Consumer dropdown menu
- Password input field
- Yellow "Create Account" button
- Link: "Already have an account? [Sign In](#)"
- Link: "[Back to Home](#)"

Figure 3 Register in Data standardizer

10.4. Dashboard

The Dashboard serves as the central command centre for the WILSON Data Standardizer, providing users with a comprehensive overview of their data standardization environment and current system status. This page displays key metrics and statistics about configured endpoints, active mapping configurations, discovered sensors, and available data tables, giving users immediate insight into the scope and health of their data standardization setup. The dashboard includes quick action buttons for common tasks such as adding new endpoints, creating mapping configurations, or accessing recently modified elements, allowing users to efficiently navigate to frequently used features. Additionally, the page shows recent activity logs and system alerts to help users stay informed about changes and potential issues that may require attention.

Figure 4 Dashboard Data standarizer

10.5. Endpoint Management

The Endpoint Management page serves as the central hub for configuring and managing connections to external data sources that provide access to sensor data and measurement information. This page allows users to add new endpoint services by specifying connection details such as base URLs, authentication credentials, and service names, creating the foundation for accessing remote data tables and their contents. Each configured endpoint represents a connection to a specific data source with its own unique settings, status monitoring, and health indicators that help users understand whether the connection is active and functioning properly. The page displays a comprehensive list of all configured endpoints with their current status, last connection test results, and basic configuration information, enabling users to quickly assess the health of their data source connections. Users can perform connection tests to verify that endpoint services are accessible and responding correctly, ensuring that data retrieval operations will function properly during mapping and standardization processes.

Figure 5 Endpoint Management in data standarizer

10.6. Tables Browser

The Tables Browser page provides users with the ability to explore and examine the data structure of tables available through their configured endpoint connections, serving as an essential discovery tool for understanding available data sources. This page connects to each configured endpoint service and retrieves comprehensive information about accessible tables, displaying them in an organized format that helps users identify which data sources contain relevant sensor information for standardization. For each discovered table, users can view basic metadata such as table names, descriptions, estimated row counts, and last update information, providing context about the data availability and freshness. The page serves as a launching point for deeper data exploration, allowing users to navigate to detailed table schema views where they can examine column structures and sample data before proceeding to create mapping configurations that will transform the source data into the canonical format.

Figure 6 Tables Browser in data standardizer

10.7. Table Details

The Table Details page offers an in-depth examination of a specific data table selected from an endpoint, providing comprehensive schema information and sample data that enables users to make informed decisions about column mapping configurations. This page displays detailed information about each column in the table including column names, data types, nullable status, and any available constraints or metadata that help users understand the structure and content of the source data. The page includes sample data rows that show actual values from the table, allowing users to see data patterns, formatting conventions, and value ranges that will inform their mapping decisions when configuring how the data should be transformed into the canonical format. Additionally, the page provides statistics about the table such as total row counts, data freshness indicators, and any notable characteristics that might affect data processing, giving users a complete picture of the data source before they proceed to create mapping configurations.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the 'Table Details' page for a table named 'medidasContadores'. The page has a dark blue theme. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a 'Back to Tables' link. Below this, the table name 'Table: medidasContadores' is displayed in large orange text, with a subtitle 'View column structure and sample data' and a yellow 'Configure Mapping' button. The main content area is titled 'Columns' and lists 12 columns in a grid. Each column entry shows the column name, its data type, and any constraints (like 'PK' for primary key).

Column Name	Data Type	Constraints
id	integer	PK
fecha	timestamp without time zone	
idcontador	integer	
nombre	character varying	
descripcion	character varying	
tensionfase1	double precision	
tensionfase2	double precision	
tensionfase3	double precision	
corrientefase1	double precision	
corrientefase2	double precision	
corrientefase3	double precision	
cosenophifase1	double precision	
cosenophifase2	double precision	
cosenophifase3	double precision	

Figure 7 Table details in data standardizer

10.8. Mapping Configuration

The Mapping Configuration page guides users through the process of defining how source table columns should be mapped to the canonical data format, implementing a structured workflow that ensures accurate and consistent data transformation. This page presents a three-step configuration process where users first identify the column containing sensor identifiers, then select the column with timestamp information, and finally choose all columns that contain measurement data to be included in the canonical data object. The interface provides intelligent suggestions and recommendations based on column names, data types, and content analysis to help users make appropriate mapping choices quickly and accurately. Real-time validation and preview functionality allow users to see how their mapping configuration will transform sample data into the canonical format.

The screenshot displays the 'Configure Sensor Data Mapping' interface. At the top, it shows the endpoint '16table=medidasContactores' and a 'Table: medidasContactores'. Below this, there are buttons for 'Preview Transformation' and 'Save Mappings'.

The 'Target Canonical Format' section shows a JSON schema:

```
{
  "sensor_id": "unique-sensor-identifier",
  "timestamp": "2025-10-14T10:30:00Z",
  "data": {
    "temperature": 23.5,
    "humidity": 65.2,
    "pressure": 1013.25
  }
}
```

The 'Source Columns' section lists columns from the source table:

- id (Integer, PK, Good for Sensor ID)
- fecha (timestamp without time zone, Good for Timestamp)
- idcontactor (Integer, Good for Sensor ID)
- nombre (character varying)
- descripcion (character varying)
- iluminacion (boolean)
- fancoil (boolean)
- uta (boolean)

The 'Required Mappings' section shows three steps:

- 1. Sensor ID Column ***: Choose the column that uniquely identifies each sensor. Selected: **idcontactor**.
- 2. Timestamp Column ***: Choose the column containing datetime information. Selected: **fecha**.
- 3. Data Columns ***: Choose all measurement/sensor value columns. Selected: **fancoil**, **iluminacion**, **uta**.

The 'Mapping Guidance' section provides instructions:

- Sensor ID Column**: Choose a column with unique sensor identifiers. Examples: device_id, sensor_name, equipment_id. Must be unique per sensor across the table.
- Timestamp Column**: Choose a datetime column. Examples: timestamp, datetime, recorded_at. Will be converted to ISO 8601 format.
- Data Columns**: Select all measurement columns. Examples: temperature, voltage, pressure. All will be grouped into a data object. Exclude ID and timestamp columns.

The 'Example Transformation' section shows:

Source Data:

```
device_id | timestamp | temp | humidity
SENSOR001 | 2025-10-14 | 23.5 | 65.2
```

Canonical Output:

```
{
  "sensor_id": "SENSOR001",
  "timestamp": "2025-10-14T10:00:00Z",
  "data": {
    "temp": 23.5,
    "humidity": 65.2
  }
}
```

The 'Mapping Summary' section indicates:

- Mapping Complete
- Sensor ID: idcontactor
- Timestamp: fecha
- Data Columns: fancoil, iluminacion, uta

An 'Example Output' is also shown at the bottom, matching the canonical format.

Figure 8 Mapping Configuration in data standardizer

10.9. Mappings Overview

The Mappings Overview page provides a centralized view of all configured column mapping configurations, displaying them in an organized layout that allows users to quickly assess their data standardization setup and manage existing configurations. This page presents each mapping configuration as a detailed card showing information about the source table, associated endpoint, and the specific column assignments for sensor identifiers, timestamps, and data fields that define how the data will be transformed. Users can review the status and details of each mapping, access editing functions to modify configurations that need adjustments, and navigate to related functionality such as viewing the source table details or accessing the sensor registry for specific mappings. The page serves as the primary management interface for data transformation rules, providing quick access to common tasks like editing mappings, viewing associated sensors, and monitoring the overall health and completeness of the data standardization configuration.

Figure 9 Mappings Overview in data standarizer

10.10. Sensor Registry

The Sensor Registry page displays the crucial relationship between original sensor identifiers found in source data tables and the universal canonical UUIDs that represent them in the standardized API, providing complete traceability and mapping transparency for data transformation processes. This page shows all discovered and registered sensors for a specific mapping configuration, displaying how each original sensor identifier from the source table has been assigned a unique canonical UUID that will be consistently used across all API responses and data queries. The page includes powerful sensor discovery functionality that automatically scans source table data to identify and register all unique sensor identifiers, creating the essential UUID mappings needed for the canonical API to function properly. Users can view and manage sensor metadata such as display names, descriptions, and sensor types, copy canonical UUIDs for use in API testing and integration, and access direct links to test the canonical API endpoints for specific sensors to verify that the data transformation and retrieval processes are working correctly.

← Back to Mappings

Sensor Registry

MAPPING CONFIGURATION
medidasContadores

View the relationship between original sensor IDs and canonical UUIDs for **medidasContadores** (Endpoint 1)

Configuration Details

Sensor ID Column: **idcontador** Timestamp Column: **fecha** Data Columns: **corrientefase1, corrientefase2, corrientefase3** Total Data Columns: **3**

Registered Sensors (18)

Each original sensor ID from your source table is mapped to a unique canonical UUID that can be used in API queries.

Original Sensor ID	Display Name	Created	Canonical UUID
43	Sensor 43	2025-10-15 12:27	6f81852a-abca-4fec-b104-49614175f6d0
54	Sensor 54	2025-10-15 12:27	bEb304fc-4ccc-4acb-bff0-15fb3c63d263
45	Sensor 45	2025-10-15 12:27	e9ab6cdd-3831-4ac9-97fc-897008feac37

Figure 10 Sensor Registry in data standardizer

11. ANNEX B. DATABASE ENDPOINT GENERATOR API DOCUMENTATION

This API provides secure, read-only access to PostgreSQL database tables. An online swagger-based documentation is available in the project server.

Security Features

- Multiple layers of read-only protection
- Connection-level read-only configuration
- Session-level read-only enforcement
- Application-level write operation blocking

Authentication

- Basic Authentication required for all endpoints

Available Operations

- List available database tables
- Get table schema information
- Query table data with pagination
- Retrieve specific records by ID

Important Notes

- This API is READ-ONLY - no data modifications possible
- All write operations are blocked at multiple levels
- Database connection is configured in read-only mode

11.1. Endpoints

data		^
GET	/api/v1/data	Get paginated data from database tables
GET	/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered	Get filtered table data
GET	/api/v1/data/{record_id}	Get a specific record by ID
GET	/api/v1/tables	List all available database tables
GET	/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema	Get table schema information

Figure 11 Endpoint generator endpoints

11.1.1. get_data_api_v1_data_get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/data \
  -H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /api/v1/data HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
};
```

```
fetch('/api/v1/data',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});
```

```
require 'rest-client'
require 'json'
```

```
headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json'
}
```

```
result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/data',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers
```

```
p JSON.parse(result)
```

```

import requests
headers = {
    'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/api/v1/data', headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/data', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
    );
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/data");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
    
```

```

BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());
    
```

```
package main
```

```
import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)
```

```
func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/data", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}
    
```

GET /api/v1/data

Get paginated data from database tables

Retrieve data from PostgreSQL tables with pagination support.

Features:

- Pagination with limit/offset
- Table selection via query parameter
- Returns total count for pagination
- Read-only access guaranteed

Example Requests:

...

GET /api/v1/data?limit=10&offset=0

GET /api/v1/data?table_name=medidasContadores&limit=5

GET /api/v1/data?table_name=contadores&limit=20&offset=100

...

Authentication: Basic Auth required (admin/admin123)

Parameters

Name	In	Type	Required	Description
limit	query	integer	false	Maximum number of records to return (max 1000)
offset	query	integer	false	Number of records to skip for pagination
table_name	query	any	false	Name of the database table to query

Example responses

200 Response

```
{
  "data": [
    {
      "id": 1,
      "name": "Record 1",
      "value": 10.5
    },
    {
      "id": 2,
      "name": "Record 2",
      "value": 20.3
    }
  ],
  "limit": 100,
  "offset": 0,
  "total": 150
}
```

Responses

Status	Meaning	Description	Schema
200	OK	Paginated list of database records with metadata	DataListResponse
422	Unprocessable Entity	Validation Error	HTTPValidationError

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBasic

11.1.2. get_filtered_data_api_v1_data__table_name__filtered_get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered?filters=string \
  -H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered?filters=string HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
};

fetch('/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered?filters=string',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered',
  params: {
    'filters' => 'array[string]'
  }, headers: headers
```

```

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
    'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered', params={
    'filters': [
        "string"
    ]
}, headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}
    
```

```

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered?filters=string");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)

func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}

GET /api/v1/data/{table_name}/filtered
Get filtered table data
    
```

Retrieve filtered data from a table using column-based filters with pagination.

Features:

- Filter by one or multiple columns with various operators
- Multiple operators: =, !=, >, <, >=, <=, LIKE, ILIKE
- Pagination support with limit/offset
- SQL injection protection through parameterized queries
- Column validation against table schema

Filter Format:

- Simple equality: `column_name:value` (defaults to = operator)
- With operator: `column_name:operator:value`

Filter Examples:

- `status:active` → WHERE status = 'active'
- `age:>=:18` → WHERE age >= 18
- `name:ILIKE:%john%` → WHERE name ILIKE '%john%'
- `idcontador:37` → WHERE idcontador = 37
- `fecha:>=:2025-01-01` → WHERE fecha >= '2025-01-01'

Example Requests:

...

```
GET /api/v1/data/medidasContadores/filtered?filters=idcontador:37&limit=5
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/contadores/filtered?filters=status:active&filters=type:electrical
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/medidasContadores/filtered?filters=idcontador:>=:30&filters=fecha:>=:2025-01-01&limit=10
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/usuarios/filtered?filters=nombre:ILIKE:%admin%&limit=20
```

...

URL Encoded Examples (for curl):

```
```bash
```

```
curl -u admin:admin123 "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/data/medidasContadores/filtered?filters=idcontador:37&limit=5"
```

```
curl -u admin:admin123 "http://localhost:8000/api/v1/data/contadores/filtered?filters=status:active"
```

...

Authentication: Basic Auth required (admin/admin123)

### Parameters

Name	In	Type	Required	Description
table_name	path	string	true	Name of the database table to query
filters	query	array[string]	true	Column filters in format 'column_name:value' or 'column_name:operator:value'
limit	query	integer	false	Maximum number of records to return (1-1000)
offset	query	integer	false	Number of records to skip for pagination

### Example responses

200 Response

```
{
 "applied_filters": [
 {
 "column_name": "status",
 "operator": "=",
 "value": "active"
 }
],
 "data": [
 {
 "email": "john@example.com",
 "id": 1,
 "name": "John Doe",
 "status": "active"
 }
],
 "limit": 10,
 "offset": 0,
 "returned_count": 1,
 "table_name": "users",
 "total_count": 75
}
```

### Responses

Status	Meaning	Description	Schema
200	OK	Filtered data retrieved successfully	FilteredDataResponse
400	Bad Request	Invalid filter format or parameters	None
404	Not Found	Table or column not found	None
422	Unprocessable Entity	Validation Error	HTTPValidationError
500	Internal Server Error	Database error	None

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBasic.

### 11.1.3. get\_data\_by\_id\_api\_v1\_data\_\_record\_id\_\_get

#### Code samples

# You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/data/{record_id} \
 -H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/{record_id} HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
 'Accept': 'application/json'
};

fetch('/api/v1/data/{record_id}',
{
 method: 'GET',

 headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
 return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
 console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
 'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/data/{record_id}',
 params: {
 }, headers: headers
```

```

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
 'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/api/v1/data/{record_id}', headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
 'Accept' => 'application/json',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
 $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/data/{record_id}', array(
 'headers' => $headers,
 'json' => $request_body,
)
);
 print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
 // handle exception or api errors.
 print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

```

```

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/data/{record_id}");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
 new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
 response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

```

**package** main

```

import (
 "bytes"
 "net/http"
)

```

**func** main() {

```

 headers := map[string][]string{
 "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
 }

```

```

 data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
 req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/data/{record_id}", data)
 req.Header = headers

```

```

 client := &http.Client{}
 resp, err := client.Do(req)
 // ...
}

```

GET /api/v1/data/{record\_id}  
 Get a specific record by ID

Retrieve a single database record by its primary key ID.

**Features:**

- Fetch by primary key (usually 'id' field)
- Automatic primary key detection
- 404 response if record not found
- Read-only access guaranteed

**Example Requests:**

...

```
GET /api/v1/data/1234
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/1234?table_name=medidasContadores
```

```
GET /api/v1/data/5678?table_name=contadores
```

...

Authentication: Basic Auth required (admin/admin123)

**Parameters**

Name	In	Type	Required	Description
record_id	path	integer	true	Primary key ID of the record to retrieve
table_name	query	any	false	Name of the database table to query

**Example responses**

200 Response

```
{
 "data": {
 "created_at": "2025-10-01T12:00:00Z",
 "id": 1,
 "name": "Sample Record",
 "value": 42.5
 }
}
```

**Responses**

Status	Meaning	Description	Schema
200	OK	Record found and returned	DataResponse
404	Not Found	Record not found	None
422	Unprocessable Entity	Validation Error	HTTPValidationError
500	Internal Server Error	Database error	None

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBasic.

#### 11.1.4. get\_available\_tables\_api\_v1\_tables\_get

##### Code samples

```
You can also use wget
curl -X GET /api/v1/tables \
 -H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /api/v1/tables HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
 'Accept': 'application/json'
};

fetch('/api/v1/tables',
{
 method: 'GET',

 headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
 return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
 console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
 'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/tables',
 params: {
 }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
```

```
'Accept': 'application/json'
}
```

```
r = requests.get('/api/v1/tables', headers = headers)
```

```
print(r.json())
```

```
<?php
```

```
require 'vendor/autoload.php';
```

```
$headers = array(
 'Accept' => 'application/json',
);
```

```
$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();
```

```
// Define array of request body.
```

```
$request_body = array();
```

```
try {
```

```
 $response = $client->request('GET', '/api/v1/tables', array(
 'headers' => $headers,
 'json' => $request_body,
));
```

```
 print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
```

```
}
```

```
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
```

```
 // handle exception or api errors.
```

```
 print_r($e->getMessage());
```

```
}
```

```
// ...
```

```
URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/tables");
```

```
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
```

```
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
```

```
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
```

```
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
 new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
```

```

String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
 response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
 "bytes"
 "net/http"
)

func main() {

 headers := map[string][]string{
 "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
 }

 data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
 req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/tables", data)
 req.Header = headers

 client := &http.Client{}
 resp, err := client.Do(req)
 // ...
}

```

GET /api/v1/tables

*List all available database tables*

Get a list of all available tables in the public schema.

Features:

- Lists all user tables (excludes system tables)
- Sorted alphabetically
- Read-only metadata access

Example Requests:

...

```
GET /api/v1/tables
```

```
...
```

Example Response:

```
```json
{
  "tables": [
    "contadores",
    "medidasContadores",
    "usuarios",
    "sensores"
  ]
}
```
```

Authentication: Basic Auth required (admin/admin123)

### Example responses

200 Response

**null**

### Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description                   | Schema |
|--------|---------|-------------------------------|--------|
| 200    | OK      | List of available table names | Inline |

### Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBasic

#### 11.1.5. get\_table\_schema\_api\_v1\_tables\_\_table\_name\_\_schema\_get

##### Code samples

# You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema \
-H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema HTTP/1.1
```

Accept: application/json

```
const headers = {
 'Accept': 'application/json'
};
```

```

fetch('/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema',
{
 method: 'GET',

 headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
 return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
 console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
 'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema',
 params: {
 }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
 'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema', headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
 'Accept' => 'application/json',

```

```

);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
 $response = $client->request('GET',"/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema', array(
 'headers' => $headers,
 'json' => $request_body,
)
);
 print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
 // handle exception or api errors.
 print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
 new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
 response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
 "bytes"
 "net/http"

```

)

```
func main() {
```

```
 headers := map[string][]string{
 "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
 }
```

```
 data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
 req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/tables/{table_name}/schema", data)
 req.Header = headers
```

```
 client := &http.Client{}
 resp, err := client.Do(req)
 // ...
}
```

GET /api/v1/tables/{table\_name}/schema  
*Get table schema information*

Retrieve detailed schema information for a specific table.

Features:

- Column names and data types
- Nullable constraints
- Default values
- Primary key identification
- Read-only metadata access

Example Requests:

...

GET /api/v1/tables/medidasContadores/schema

GET /api/v1/tables/contadores/schema

GET /api/v1/tables/usuarios/schema

...

Example Response:

```
```json
{
  "table_name": "medidasContadores",
  "schema": [
    {
```

```

        "column_name": "id",
        "data_type": "integer",
        "is_nullable": false,
        "column_default": "nextval('...')",
        "is_primary_key": true
    },
    {
        "column_name": "fecha",
        "data_type": "timestamp without time zone",
        "is_nullable": false,
        "column_default": null,
        "is_primary_key": false
    }
]
}
...
    
```

Authentication: Basic Auth required (admin/admin123)

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|------------|------|--------|----------|----------------------------|
| table_name | path | string | true | Name of the database table |

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|-----------------------|--------------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Table schema information | Inline |
| 404 | Not Found | Table not found | None |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |
| 500 | Internal Server Error | Database error | None |

Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBasic.

11.1.6. health_check_health_get

Code samples

```

# You can also use wget
curl -X GET /health \
-H 'Accept: application/json'
    
```

GET /health HTTP/1.1

Accept: application/json

```

const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
};

fetch('/health',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/health',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/health', headers = headers)
    
```

```

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/health', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
    );
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/health");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
    
```

```

}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)

func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/health", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}

```

GET /health

Health check endpoint

Check if the API service and database connection are healthy

Example responses

200 Response

Null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|---------|-----------------------|--------|
| 200 | OK | Service health status | Inline |

Response Schema

This operation does not require authentication

11.2. Schemas

11.2.1. ColumnFilter

```
{
  "column_name": "status",
  "operator": "=",
  "value": "active"
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|-------------|--------|----------|--------------|--|
| column_name | string | true | none | Name of the column to filter by |
| value | string | true | none | Value to filter for |
| operator | string | false | none | Comparison operator (=, !=, LIKE, ILIKE, >, <, >=, <=) |

11.2.2. DataListResponse

```
{
  "data": [
    {
      "id": 1,
      "name": "Record 1",
      "value": 10.5
    },
    {
      "id": 2,
      "name": "Record 2",
      "value": 20.3
    }
  ],
  "limit": 100,
  "offset": 0,
  "total": 150
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|--------|----------|----------|--------------|---|
| data | [object] | true | none | List of database records |
| total | integer | true | none | Total number of records available |
| limit | integer | true | none | Maximum records returned in this response |
| offset | integer | true | none | Number of records skipped |

11.2.3. DataResponse

```
{
  "data": {
    "created_at": "2025-10-01T12:00:00Z",
    "id": 1,
    "name": "Sample Record",
    "value": 42.5
  }
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|------|--------|----------|--------------|------------------------------------|
| data | object | true | none | Database record as key-value pairs |

11.2.4. FilteredDataResponse

```
{
  "applied_filters": [
    {
      "column_name": "status",
      "operator": "=",
      "value": "active"
    }
  ],
  "data": [
    {
      "email": "john@example.com",
      "id": 1,
      "name": "John Doe",
      "status": "active"
    }
  ],
  "limit": 10,
  "offset": 0,
  "returned_count": 1,
  "table_name": "users",
  "total_count": 75
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|-----------------|----------------|----------|--------------|--|
| table_name | string | true | none | Name of the queried table |
| data | [object] | true | none | Array of filtered table rows |
| total_count | integer | true | none | Total number of rows matching filters |
| returned_count | integer | true | none | Number of rows returned in this response |
| limit | integer | true | none | Applied row limit |
| offset | integer | true | none | Applied row offset |
| applied_filters | [ColumnFilter] | true | none | Filters that were applied to the query |

11.2.5. HTTPValidationError

```
{
  "detail": [
    {
      "loc": [
        "string"
      ],
      "msg": "string",
      "type": "string"
    }
  ]
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|--------|-------------------|----------|--------------|-------------|
| detail | [ValidationError] | false | none | none |

11.2.6. ValidationError

```
{
  "loc": [
    "string"
  ],
  "msg": "string",
  "type": "string"
}
```

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|------|---------|----------|--------------|-------------|
| loc | [anyOf] | true | none | none |

anyOf

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|--------------------|--------|----------|--------------|-------------|
| » <i>anonymous</i> | string | false | none | none |

or

| Name | Type | Required | Restrictions | Description |
|--------------------|---------|----------|--------------|-------------|
| » <i>anonymous</i> | integer | false | none | none |
| msg | string | true | none | none |
| type | string | true | none | none |

12. ANNEX C. DATA STANDARIZER API DOCUMENTATION

A service to translate endpoint data into canonical format. Since most of the API endpoints are UI driven we only show the endpoint designed for machine-to-machine interactions. An online swagger-based documentation is available in the project server.

12.1. Endpoints

| authentication | | ^ |
|----------------|---|-----|
| POST | /token Login For Access Token | 🔒 ↓ |
| default | | ^ |
| GET | /health Health Check | ↓ |
| canonical | | ^ |
| GET | /api/v1/canonical/data Query canonical sensor data | 🔒 ↓ |
| GET | /api/v1/canonical/sensors List canonical sensors | 🔒 ↓ |
| GET | /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id} Get canonical sensor details | 🔒 ↓ |
| GET | /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data Get sensor-specific data | 🔒 ↓ |

Figure 12 Data standarizer endpoints

12.1.1. health_check_health_get

Code samples

```
# You can also use wget
curl -X GET /health \
  -H 'Accept: application/json'
```

```
GET /health HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
};
```

```
fetch('/health',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
```

```

        return res.json();
    }).then(function(body) {
        console.log(body);
    });

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.get '/health',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.get('/health', headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
  'Accept' => 'application/json',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {

```

```

$response = $client->request('GET','/health', array(
    'headers' => $headers,
    'json' => $request_body,
))
);
print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/health");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)

func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
    }

```

```

data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/health", data)
req.Header = headers

client := &http.Client{}
resp, err := client.Do(req)
// ...
}
    
```

GET /health
Health Check

Health check endpoint

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|---------|---------------------|--------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Inline |

Response Schema

This operation does not require authentication

12.1.2. login_for_access_token_token_post

Code samples

You can also use wget

```

curl -X POST /token \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded' \
  -H 'Accept: application/json'
    
```

POST /token HTTP/1.1

Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded

Accept: application/json

```

const inputBody = {
  "grant_type": "string",
  "username": "string",
  "password": "pa$$word",
  "scope": "",
  "client_id": "string",
  "client_secret": "string"
}
    
```

```

};

const headers = {
  'Content-Type': 'application/x-www-form-urlencoded',
  'Accept': 'application/json'
};

fetch('/token',
{
  method: 'POST',
  body: inputBody,
  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Content-Type' => 'application/x-www-form-urlencoded',
  'Accept' => 'application/json'
}

result = RestClient.post '/token',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
  'Content-Type': 'application/x-www-form-urlencoded',
  'Accept': 'application/json'
}

r = requests.post('/token', headers = headers)

print(r.json())
    
```

```
<?php
```

```
require 'vendor/autoload.php';
```

```
$headers = array(
    'Content-Type' => 'application/x-www-form-urlencoded',
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
);
```

```
$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();
```

```
// Define array of request body.
```

```
$request_body = array();
```

```
try {
```

```
    $response = $client->request('POST', '/token', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
```

```
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
```

```
}
```

```
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
```

```
    // handle exception or api errors.
```

```
    print_r($e->getMessage());
```

```
}
```

```
// ...
```

```
URL obj = new URL("/token");
```

```
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
```

```
con.setRequestMethod("POST");
```

```
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
```

```
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
```

```
String inputLine;
```

```
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
```

```
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
```

```
    response.append(inputLine);
```

```
}
```

```
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());
```

```
package main
```

```
import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)
```

```
func main() {
```

```
    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Content-Type": []string{"application/x-www-form-urlencoded"},
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
    }
```

```
    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("POST", "/token", data)
    req.Header = headers
```

```
    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}
```

POST /token
Login For Access Token

OAuth2 compatible token login for API access. Use this endpoint in Swagger UI or API clients to get a bearer token.

Body parameter

```
grant_type: string
username: string
password: pa$$word
scope: ""
client_id: string
client_secret: string
```

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|------|------|--|----------|-------------|
| body | body | Body_login_for_access_token_token_post | true | none |

Example responses

200 Response

```
{
  "access_token": "string",
  "token_type": "string"
}
```

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|----------------------|---------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Token |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |

This operation does not require authentication

12.1.3. get_canonical_data_api_v1_canonical_data_get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/canonical/data?sensor_ids=string \
  -H 'Accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {access-token}'
```

```
GET /api/v1/canonical/data?sensor_ids=string HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json',
  'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
};

fetch('/api/v1/canonical/data?sensor_ids=string',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
});
```

```

    }).then(function(body) {
        console.log(body);
    });

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
    'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/canonical/data',
    params: {
        'sensor_ids' => 'array[string]'
    }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
    'Accept': 'application/json',
    'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
}

r = requests.get('/api/v1/canonical/data', params={
    'sensor_ids': [
        "string"
    ]
}, headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
    'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}',
);
    
```

```

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/canonical/data', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/canonical/data?sensor_ids=string");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)
    
```

```
func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
        "Authorization": []string{"Bearer {access-token}"},
    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/canonical/data", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}
```

GET /api/v1/canonical/data
Query canonical sensor data

Query canonical sensor data by sensor IDs and date range

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|------------|-------|---------------|----------|--------------------------------|
| sensor_ids | query | array[string] | true | List of canonical sensor UUIDs |
| start_date | query | any | false | Start date for filtering |
| end_date | query | any | false | End date for filtering |
| limit | query | integer | false | Maximum number of records |
| offset | query | integer | false | Number of records to skip |

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|----------------------|---------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Inline |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |

Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBearer

12.1.4. list_canonical_sensors_api_v1_canonical_sensors_get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors \
  -H 'Accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {access-token}'
```

```
GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json',
  'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
};

fetch('/api/v1/canonical/sensors',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json',
  'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/canonical/sensors',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)
```

import requests

```
headers = {
    'Accept': 'application/json',
    'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
}
```

```
r = requests.get('/api/v1/canonical/sensors', headers = headers)
```

```
print(r.json())
```

<?php

```
require 'vendor/autoload.php';
```

```
$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
    'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}',
);
```

```
$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();
```

```
// Define array of request body.
```

```
$request_body = array();
```

```
try {
```

```
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/canonical/sensors', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
```

```
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
```

```
}
```

```
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
```

```
    // handle exception or api errors.
```

```
    print_r($e->getMessage());
```

```
}
```

```
// ...
```

```
URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/canonical/sensors");
```

```
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
```

```

con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)

func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
        "Authorization": []string{"Bearer {access-token}"},
    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/canonical/sensors", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}

```

GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors
List canonical sensors

List user's canonical sensors with metadata, optionally filtered by endpoint

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|------|----|------|----------|-------------|
|------|----|------|----------|-------------|

| | | | | |
|-------------|-------|-----|-------|---------------------------------|
| endpoint_id | query | any | false | Filter sensors by endpointer ID |
|-------------|-------|-----|-------|---------------------------------|

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|----------------------|---------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Inline |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |

Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBearer

12.1.5. get_canonical_sensor_api_v1_canonical_sensors__sensor_id__get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```
curl -X GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id} \
  -H 'Accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {access-token}'
```

```
GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id} HTTP/1.1
```

```
Accept: application/json
```

```
const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json',
  'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
};

fetch('/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
```

```

        console.log(body);
    });

    require 'rest-client'
    require 'json'

    headers = {
      'Accept' => 'application/json',
      'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}'
    }

    result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}',
      params: {
      }, headers: headers

    p JSON.parse(result)

    import requests
    headers = {
      'Accept': 'application/json',
      'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
    }

    r = requests.get('/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}', headers = headers)

    print(r.json())

    <?php

    require 'vendor/autoload.php';

    $headers = array(
      'Accept' => 'application/json',
      'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}',
    );

    $client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

    // Define array of request body.
    $request_body = array();
    
```

```

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());

package main

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)

func main() {

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
        "Authorization": []string{"Bearer {access-token}"},
    }

```

```

    }

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}", data)
    req.Header = headers

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
}

```

GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}
Get canonical sensor details

Get specific canonical sensor details by UUID

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|-----------|------|--------|----------|-------------|
| sensor_id | path | string | true | none |

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|----------------------|---------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Inline |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |

Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBearer

12.1.6. get_sensor_data_api_v1_canonical_sensors__sensor_id__data_get

Code samples

You can also use wget

```

curl -X GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data \
  -H 'Accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {access-token}'

```

GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data HTTP/1.1

Accept: application/json

```

const headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json',
  'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
};

fetch('/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data',
{
  method: 'GET',

  headers: headers
})
.then(function(res) {
  return res.json();
}).then(function(body) {
  console.log(body);
});

require 'rest-client'
require 'json'

headers = {
  'Accept' => 'application/json',
  'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}'
}

result = RestClient.get '/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data',
  params: {
  }, headers: headers

p JSON.parse(result)

import requests
headers = {
  'Accept': 'application/json',
  'Authorization': 'Bearer {access-token}'
}
    
```

```

r = requests.get('/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data', headers = headers)

print(r.json())

<?php

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

$headers = array(
    'Accept' => 'application/json',
    'Authorization' => 'Bearer {access-token}',
);

$client = new \GuzzleHttp\Client();

// Define array of request body.
$request_body = array();

try {
    $response = $client->request('GET','/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data', array(
        'headers' => $headers,
        'json' => $request_body,
    )
);
    print_r($response->getBody()->getContents());
}
catch (\GuzzleHttp\Exception\BadResponseException $e) {
    // handle exception or api errors.
    print_r($e->getMessage());
}

// ...

URL obj = new URL("/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data");
URLConnection con = (URLConnection) obj.openConnection();
con.setRequestMethod("GET");
int responseCode = con.getResponseCode();
BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(
    new InputStreamReader(con.getInputStream()));
String inputLine;
    
```

```

StringBuffer response = new StringBuffer();
while ((inputLine = in.readLine()) != null) {
    response.append(inputLine);
}
in.close();
System.out.println(response.toString());
    
```

package main

```

import (
    "bytes"
    "net/http"
)
    
```

func main() {

```

    headers := map[string][]string{
        "Accept": []string{"application/json"},
        "Authorization": []string{"Bearer {access-token}"},
    }
    
```

```

    data := bytes.NewBuffer([]byte{jsonReq})
    req, err := http.NewRequest("GET", "/api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data", data)
    req.Header = headers
    
```

```

    client := &http.Client{}
    resp, err := client.Do(req)
    // ...
    
```

GET /api/v1/canonical/sensors/{sensor_id}/data

Get sensor-specific data

Get data for a specific canonical sensor with date filtering

Parameters

| Name | In | Type | Required | Description |
|------------|-------|---------|----------|---------------------------|
| sensor_id | path | string | true | none |
| start_date | query | any | false | Start date for filtering |
| end_date | query | any | false | End date for filtering |
| limit | query | integer | false | Maximum number of records |
| offset | query | integer | false | Number of records to skip |

Example responses

200 Response

null

Responses

| Status | Meaning | Description | Schema |
|--------|----------------------|---------------------|---------------------|
| 200 | OK | Successful Response | Inline |
| 422 | Unprocessable Entity | Validation Error | HTTPValidationError |

Response Schema

To perform this operation, you must be authenticated by means of one of the following methods: HTTPBearer

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